

V14A-08: Exploration of the Mata Submarine Volcano Group Reveals Volcano-Tectonic-Hydrothermal Links

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Abstract:

Discovered in 2008 by multibeam seabed mapping and water column plumes, the Mata submarine volcano group comprises 9, young, intra-plate seamounts in the arc-adjacent portion of the NE Lau Basin (SW Pacific Ocean). Exploration by ROV in 2009 (TN234), 2012 (RR1211) and 2017 (FK171110) has revealed details of their geology and biogeography. Relatively small (0.5-1.5 km tall) and closely-spaced (some overlap at their bases), they display a variety of structures, eruption deposit styles, apparent volcanic eruption frequency, and hydrothermal venting styles, revealing volcano-tectonic interplays at youthful volcanoes. All are elongate, with sub-parallel rift zones aligned with regional scarp directions and perpendicular to neighboring terrain formed at the nearby Northeast Lau Spreading Center. West Mata, the largest and currently most active, has a high proportion of volcanoclastic material in the edifice and a distinctive stratovolcano shape, as does East Mata, its nearest neighbor. The 7 northern Mata volcanoes display a significant range of depth, height, volume, and structural complexity, with a higher proportion of lava than pyroclasts and very young (fresh, unaltered, non-sedimented) lavas occurring on 5 of them (Ua, Tolu, Fa, Ono, Fitu). All of the Matas erupt Boninite, a high-T, high Mg-andesite found primarily in subduction zones and previously only known in ancient, non-active volcanic settings. Mata magmas show a large range in composition, crystal content and gas content that likely contribute to the landforms (e.g., very steep constructional slopes, flat-topped platforms, extensive fragmental deposits), eruption styles, and volcano structure. The Matas are fed from a distributed magma system that collects and does not homogenize parent melts. West and East Mata volcanoes support diffuse flow hydrothermal systems. Active focused-flow hydrothermal systems occur on 4 N. Mata volcanoes (Fa, Tolu, Ono, Fitu), with an inactive system at Mata Taha. Each has distinct vent field sizes and locations on the volcanoes (summit, base, other), and chimney sizes, shapes and spacing. Vent-associated faunal assemblages at diffuse (shrimp-dominated) and focused (dominantly mussels, gastropods, polychaetes) flow sites have different community structures correlating with setting and heat source.

Plain language description (200 word max):

Small, closely-spaced, active submarine volcanoes in Tonga reveal a range of eruption conditions and volcano construction styles, in turn reflecting how magma is formed, delivered and accumulated in the crust before being erupted there. The volcanoes have active hydrothermal systems that vary a lot in

things like chimney size, shape, spacing, and vent field size and apparent longevity, which relate to how the volcanoes themselves are built over time. Our group has explored these volcanoes in detail over several expeditions and will present an overview of the most important observations and volcano characteristics, with relevance to how volcanoes grow and evolve in their earliest stages, and the geology and ecology of the hydrothermal system they support.